

Weather Forecasting For All Regions Of Kerala: A Machine Learning Approach

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Abstract— Many operations in the primary sector, such as agriculture, rely on the weather for their success. Traditional weather forecasting technologies are becoming less effective and time consuming as the climate changes at such a rapid rate these days. To address these issues, better and more dedicated weather forecasting procedures are required. It predict an impact on the economy and lives of people in a country. This project's main purpose to emerge a weather prediction system that can be used in remote locations. Data analytics and machine learning approaches such as random forest classifier and Decision tree classifier are used to forecast meteorological conditions. The goal of this research is to build a low-cost, portable weather predicting device.

Keywords—Random forest classification and Logistic Regression.

I. INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is Kerala's most important industry. The expansion of this sector has a significant impact on major macroeconomic goals such as business conditions, population ageing, lifestyle enhancements, food security, and so on. Agriculture is the primary source of income for the majority of Kerala, whether directly or indirectly. The population density in Kerala's northern region is extremely low. In addition, Kerala's northern region has a large agricultural area that produces a wide range of crops and vegetables. As a result, the northern region of the district has a significant impact on Kerala's agriculture and economy.. There are 14 districts in Kerala: Trivandrum, Kollam, Aalapuzha, Idukki, Kottayam, Pathanamthitta, Ernakulam, Thrissur, Palakkad, Malappuram, Kozhikode, Wayanad, Kannur, Kasaragod. The total area is "38,863" square kilometres, and the population is 3.46 crore. Kerala's northern region has a diverse climate. During the summer, the weather is excessively hot, and the temperature get up to such an extent that finding relief is difficult; the temperature is nearly 40°-42° Celsius. The rainy season lasts only a few weeks. The amount of rain falling in these areas is gradually decreasing. There is a wide range of situations during the winter season. On rare occasions, temperatures as low as 5°-8° Celsius have been recorded. Weather irregularities cause drought, water, and food shortages, as well as long-term environmental consequences. It has long-term socioeconomic and health implications for people.

The method for detecting weather forecasting :

A machine learning algorithm, the random forest classification algorithm that uses an ensemble learning

method to combine two or more machine learning models to create a single model. It works by training a large number of decision trees and then displaying the classification modes of various trees.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In [1,] A Raspberry Pi 3 B application has been developed for the proposed system. This application Forecasts the possibility of rain on the current day using real- time data from humidity, temperature, and pressure sensors.

In [2,] The Bangladesh Meteorological Department provided thirty years of historical weather data on temperature, rain, wind, and humidity for this experiment (BMD).The Extreme Machine Learning (ELM) model outperforms the Artificial Neural Network (ANN) model, with a 95% accuracy rate.

In [3,] Weather is made up of numerous parameters such as rainfall, precipitation, wind speed, and so on. Environmental weather forecasting is a difficult task for researchers but it has sparked a lot of interest in recent years.

In [4,] Weather Prediction is a technique for predicting what the atmosphere will be like in a specific location by using scientific knowledge and weather conditions. In other words, it is a method of anticipating cloud cover, rain, snow, wind speed, and temperature. Perfect weather predictions are required for daily activities, and it is one of the most difficult problems that the world faces due to the multidimensional and nonlinear nature of the data.

In [5,] The author used hourly perceptions from 40 present weather sensors spread across Australia to compare the hypothesis to ET0 Using the NWP estimate every day ET0 was found to be superior to using the long-haul month to month mean ET0 for lead times up to 6 days, but the long-haul month to month mean was better beyond that.

In [6,] The first numerical attempt to predict weather required a larger workforce. Weather prediction has returned to the early models in terms of similarity, thanks to the advancement of powerful computers and better modelling techniques. The simple-basic equations are then used in Weather Prediction as forecast equations.

In [7,] Agriculture is our country's primary economic pillar. The crop price has fluctuated to a greater extent in recent

years due to uncertain climate trends and other price fluctuations. Farmers continue to ignore these uncertainties, causing crop damage and massive losses. They are unaware of the crop type that would be most beneficial to them. Crops are harmed as a result of their lack of knowledge about various crop diseases and their specific treatments. This system is convenient and simple to use. Rainfall, wholesale price index, month, and year are the variables considered for prediction. As a result, the system provides farmers with an advance forecast

III. MOTIVATION

This will make it difficult for us to determine whether or not rain will fall. This should not have happened. This is useful if there is a chance of flooding. It will aid humans in protecting their agriculture.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this paper is to identify a Machine Learning model that can accurately classify weather conditions using the dataset provided. The model should be able to correctly determine whether or not it is raining. The dataset has two sections: training and testing. More data should be used to train the model in order to improve learning accuracy. This model's output can be used to create a news classification system. Weather forecasting will be learned using the Random Forest classifier.

The steps that require to be followed are:

1. Data Collection
2. Data Pre-processing
3. Model Building
4. Analyzing
5. Result

A. Data Collection : The user has a dataset for detecting climate conditions in Kerala, and its attributes are used to train the model. There are 316 rows and 2 columns in the dataset.

B. Data Pre-processing: This is the first step in any machine learning method. This procedure includes data cleansing, transformation, and reduction. All of this is done to improve the effectiveness of the data. The data can be processed to improve the accuracy of our model. In order for the classification to be correct.

1. **Cleaning Data** – Initially, the data is cleaned. This is where users remove the unwanted.
2. **Removing Stop words** - The stop words are

removed from the datasets. These are the most common and have little significance in the text. This can be done to improve model accuracy.

Splitting of Data - After cleaning the data, it is divided into training and testing datasets. Following that, the data selected for training is used to train our model.

C. Machine Learning : This is used to detect climate condition. The machine learning algorithms are used to detect rain tomorrow, that will check the news given. There are different classifiers present to detect the fake news. The classifier accuracy relies on how it is trained. A classifier should need high accuracy.

1. **Random Forest Classification:** Random Forest is a classifier that aggregates the results of a number of decision trees on different subsets of a dataset to improve the dataset's predicted accuracy.
2. **Logistic Regression:** Logistic Regression is a supervised learning algorithm. It is used to forecast the categorical dependent variable from a set of independent variables.

V. BUILD MODEL

The main step in detecting weather prediction is model construction. The algorithms are used while building the model.

The procedures are as follows:

1. Import the packages that are necessary
2. Add the data into a Data Frame, then get the shape of data
3. Then split the dataset into training and testing datasets
4. Then, fit and transform train and test set
5. Initialize Random Forest Classifier

Then identify on test set and calculate the

accuracy and confusion matrix of the model.

```
print(confusion_matrix(y_test, predictions))
print(classification_report(y_test, predictions))
print(accuracy_score(y_test, predictions))
```

The accuracy is 96.4%

V1. RESULT

Based on the dataset provided, the weather prediction can be classified as rainy or not rainy. The Random Forest classifier produces accurate and correct results. The dataset contains yes or no answers for rain tomorrow from various areas. This has been classified, and the model correctly predicted rain for tomorrow.

VII. CONCLUSION

The Random Forest Classifier is used in this paper to detect climate conditions. This is using the best features to detect Rainfall. In this case, the user implemented a solution by first processing the data and then using to derive some dataset features. The user then used the Random Forest Classifier to create a model that classified climate conditions.

The work has a lot of potential in the future. The dataset can be expanded, and any other machine algorithms or tools can be used to predict rain tomorrow. The other aspect is that key sources of weather prediction can be identified using Logistic Regression.

VIII. REFERENCES

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